

EMPHASIZE THE SOCIAL NATURE OF LEARNING

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Annotation: This article outlines and discusses the Social Nature of Learning as it applies to an overall approach to Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) within second language education and suggests that second language teachers can actively implement more student - student collaboration in their classes so that the students can further develop their second language skills and abilities.

Key phrases: Investigation, Planning, Implementing, Classroom implications, Group work, Snowball;

One of the basic tenets of the social nature of all learning is that we can learn from each other rather than trying to learn by ourselves. This idea can be carried over into our second language classrooms when we realize that our students can also learn from and with their peers. Whereas in the traditional approach or paradigm, the rules often were, "Eyes on your own paper," and "No talking to your neighbor," the goal in the Social Nature of Learning essential is to encourage our students to share with their peers and their teachers. Indeed, research suggests that second language students learn from and teach others all the time, especially when they are not in formal teaching settings and more specifically within a CLT approach, as have noted, it is actually expected that second language students will interact with their classmates in speech and writing during class activities as well as outside of class. In order for this to happen though, both second language teachers and their students need to be aware of cooperative learning skills.

Cooperative learning (also known as collaborative learning) is one of the most researched methods in all of education, with thousands of studies having been done involving a wide range of students, as to age, ethnicity, and nationality, and a wide range of subject areas, including second language. These studies suggest that cooperative learning can lead to gains of cognitive and affective variables. What should be emphasized is that it is seldom useful for teachers to just ask students to form groups and work together. Instead, preparation must take place. The literature on cooperative learning offers principles and techniques to aid in this preparation. Many students need some preparation for group activities as they may not be accustomed to working with classmates on academic tasks. Instead, they may have mostly experienced teacher-fronted instruction. To prepare students to cooperate, second language teachers often include explicit instruction in cooperative skills. The teaching of cooperative skills is a cooperative learning principle.

Johnson and Johnson explain a useful six-step procedure for facilitating students' regular use of cooperative skills that can be used in second language classrooms:

- ❖ Students understand why a particular skill is important.

- ❖ Students know the words, phrases, gestures, etc. typical of use of that one skill.
- ❖ Students practice the skill in isolation, e.g., they do a game or role play that features the skill.
- ❖ Students use the skill during a cooperative learning activity involving regular course content.

Another means second language teachers have of promoting collaboration in their classrooms is to foster an overall atmosphere in which cooperation acts not just as a methodology for second language learning, but also a topic in itself for learning, and as a value embraced in all learning activities. Examples of relation as a topic for learning would be second language students writing compositions about the times that they have collaborated with others. To establish cooperation as a value, the class as a group can look at what processes in the school, such as norm-referenced evaluation and in society, such as contests with only one winner, promote competition as a value. It should be noted that the aim is not to eliminate competition or individual work; the aim is to achieve a better balance.

One way to encourage students to think in terms of cooperating with others, in particular others outside the class involves service learning projects. Service learning is the combination of service to others with learning related to students' course curriculum. Learning could be added to the same experience in several ways:

- Investigation. Students could, work in pairs to study the eating habits of other students. Pairs, where possible would be formed by people with different first language backgrounds; if the entire class has a common L1, students could decide to devote a percentage of the time to speaking the second language (or L2) and could study vocabulary they would need in that discussion.
- Planning. Before beginning their service learning actions, students could discuss what would be a good project to do toward improving people's eating habits.
- Implementing. Students could prepare talks, posters, flyers to encourage others to eat more wisely and then could arrange to do the talks and expand the materials they had prepared. These service learning activities provide opportunities for students to learn together for a purpose other than to get a high score on an exam, although the learning that takes place might lead to higher exam scores.

Classroom implications: Group work - The most common way that teachers can implement this view of learning as a social activity is by the use of cooperative learning activities in their second language classes. As noted above, cooperative learning offers second language teachers many ideas for how they can go beyond merely asking students to work together in pairs or groups. Different techniques will be appropriate with different learning goals and will match with different views of teaching; furthermore, techniques can be adapted to fit particular learning situations.

We now outline and discuss two group techniques: *Snowball* and *Building Community*. *Snowball* is actually two techniques in one: *Forward Snowball* and *Reverse Snowball*.

Forward Snowball involves students in working together to *generate* ideas, and in *Reverse Snowball*, students choose from among the ideas their group has *generated*. *Forward*

Snowball is used for brainstorming and highlights the benefit of heterogeneity because it is good for gathering as many ideas or as much information as possible.

- ✓ Step 1 – Each group member works alone to list ideas or information.
- ✓ Step 2 – Pairs explain their lists to each other and then make a combined list. Duplications are eliminated.
- ✓ Step 3 – Pair One and Pair Two get together and make a combined list. Duplications are eliminated.

Forward Snowball is also useful for teambuilding (creating bonds among group members) because it provides dramatic proof that two (or more) heads really are better than one. Within second language teaching such as an English as a second language (ESL) class, *Forward Snowball* can be used as follows: The teacher writes a word on the board, such as “important.” Students do *Forward Snowball* to see how many words they can generate using the letters of “important.” Perhaps they can use various aids, such as electronic dictionaries and websites, to find more words.

In *Forward Snowball*, the group’s list gets bigger and bigger, however, in *Reverse Snowball*, it gets smaller. Thus, this technique builds analysis and evaluation skills as in the following steps:

- ✚ Step 1 – Each group member works alone to list ideas or information.
- ✚ Step 2 – Pairs explain their lists to each other and then make a list of only those items that appear on both lists or only those that they think are the best.
- ✚ Step 3 – Two pairs repeat the same process.

Reverse Snowball could work as follows: Each group member lists four examples of good writing in a particular text. By Step 3 of *Reverse Snowball*, they try to agree on the best example of good writing in the text and prepare to explain their choice.

Snowball is a useful cooperative learning technique because each member works alone first and then presents to the group, thus students are discouraged from either doing nothing or, the opposite, attempting to dominate the group. The group has a common goal, e.g., in *Forward Snowball*, their goal is to make a long list, and each group member contributes to that goal. Also, the group has a single product and this encourages them to work together.

Building community - Important factors in successful collaboration are feelings of caring, trust, and safety. Students are more likely to ask for help, take risks, and share with others in an atmosphere in which people care about, respect, and protect one another. At the same time that we are part of a community, we also maintain our individual identities. Creating such an atmosphere takes time and skilled effort.

Project work - Another way second language students can be encouraged to work collaboratively together is by engaging in project work. Projects, such as those involving service learning, offer students an opportunity to break down the artificial walls that often separate them from the wider world. Projects can take many forms and can last anywhere from 30 minutes to several months. One cooperative learning method for facilitating longer-term projects is Group Investigation.

Here, the class functions as a group of groups, with the class choosing an overall theme, such as careers, and each group deciding to study one career, such as tennis instructor, or one aspect of careers, such as how to be promoted or achieve a salary increase. Within each group,

members make a plan, divide up the work, report back to and consult each other frequently, and put together a report to present to the other groups. Group activities can also play a role in the groups' presentation. Rather than each group, one at a time, coming to the front to present, while their classmates sit motionless soaking in the presentation, group activities can be used here as well. For example, the presenters can give their audience issues to discuss with a partner, or the audience members can interview each other. Group Investigation is very similar to what is perhaps now a better-known method, Problem-based Learning.

Grading group / project work: One important question we should consider at this stage is, should group members all receive the same grade? If students have worked together on a project or some other task, giving everyone in the group the same grade makes sense for several reasons:

- ❖ Many times in life, groups succeed or fail together. For instance, if people are working together to support or oppose a ballot initiative, they all win or lose, regardless of how much each contributed to the effort.
- ❖ Positive interdependence may increase when students all receive the same grade. Thus, students may be more willing to ask for and give each other help.
- ❖ Determining how much each student contributed to their group can be very difficult.

At the same time, a number of good reasons can be given for why group members should each receive a separate grade such as:

- People looking at students' grade, such as university admissions officers, may have difficulty interpreting what a group grade says about an individual student's ability and work.
- The same student could get a different grade depending on their groupmates. With higher achieving and more motivated groupmates, a higher grade would be likely.
- Students may be demotivated if they feel their grade doesn't clearly reflect what they themselves have contributed.

A third option when grades are used to accompany group activities lies in using a combination of individual and group grading. Consequently, second language teachers have a very important role to play when setting up cooperative learning activities in their classes and these roles along with student roles, will be outlined in the following sections.

In addition to the above activities we suggest several ways by which the materials teachers use to accomplish these activities can promote collaboration among second language students. These include the following:

- The materials or teachers' guides that accompany them can give specific suggestions for which activities to do via collaboration among students and how such collaboration should be organized.
- Students and teachers can use their own knowledge and experience to decide these issues.

Role of teachers - When teachers use a Social Nature of Learning focus within a CLT approach to second language education they will usually:

- ❖ Be observers, noticing such phenomena as how well students are working together, their understanding of the material, and the process by which they are going about their work.

- ❖ Participate in work similar to what students are doing, either alone or as a group member. For instance, if students are doing science projects, they can join a group or be doing a project of their own, perhaps with people outside a school, e.g., a local environmental organization.
- ❖ Give students space to try to learn on their own. The way that most teachers use group activities is to first give some teacher input and then have a group activity in which students use in some way what the teacher has taught.

Role of students: Students play a wide range of roles as they interact with peers and others. Within a group, possible roles include the following:

- ❖ *Facilitator* (also called Coach) – keeps the group on task and checks that everyone knows what the instructions are
- ❖ *Time Keeper* – keeps track of the time limits
- ❖ *Recorder* – keeps notes on what the group has discussed – these can be in normal note form or in the shape of a graphic organizer, such as word webs or mind maps
- ❖ *Reporter* – reports the group's work to other groups or the whole class
- ❖ *Materials Manager* – makes sure the group has the materials it needs and that these are properly taken care of
- ❖ *Questioner* – asks questions to prompt the group to go more deeply and broadly into their task

Conclusion: To understand and promote learning, we look not only at individuals but also at the people who make up their world and the connections among them. These people include not only teachers, but also peers, and others in the community. This article has suggested that cooperation is valued over competing or working alone, although there is still a place for competition and individual work. When students collaborate they all play leadership roles. The article suggests that we focus greater attention on the Social Nature of Learning in our second language classes rather than on students as separate, decontextualized individuals because ultimately this will make second language learning more accessible and more enjoyable for our students.

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